

ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA)

Ginjinder Kaur¹, Aayushi Walia², Pupinder Kaur³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Human Genetics, Punjabi University, Patiala

²Research Scholar, Department of Human Genetics, Punjabi University, Patiala

³Research Scholar, Department of Human Genetics, Punjabi University, Patiala

***Corresponding Author:** Ms. Aayushi Walia, Research Scholar, Department of Human Genetics, Punjabi University, Patiala

Article History

Received: 27/03/2026

Accepted: 18/04/2026

Article ID:

RRBB/11_2026

Corresponding Author:

E-Mail: Email:

aayushi_rs25@pbi.ac.in

Abstract

Background: Coronary heart disease is one of the leading cause of sudden cardiac death. Genetics play 40-60% role in the pathogenesis of disease, making it an important biomarker for determining risk in the population of Malwa region of Punjab. The gene *F2* or Coagulation Factor II is responsible for formation of an activated serine protease thrombin. This activated thrombin enzyme converts fibrinogen to fibrin during the formation of blood clot, by initiating aggregation of platelets in the process of thrombosis and hemostasis.

Methods: The case-control study was done to check the polymorphism in SNP. A total of 400 blood samples were taken and DNA was extracted using salting out method. PCR-RFLP was done to detect mutation in SNP rs1799963 using *HindIII* restriction enzyme and specific set of primers. Statistical analysis was done to check the significance of results.

Results: The results of genotyping showed that both the case and control groups had greater percentage of wild allele type whereas only CHD patients had a mutant allele. The differences in allele frequencies were statistically significant for cases and controls ($p = 0.0001$, OR = 0.025; 95% CI = 0.001-0.43). For wild type G allele, the cases had a frequency of 95.5% (382/400) and for controls, it was 100% (400/400) whereas, for

mutant allele A, the cases showed a frequency of 4.5% (18/400) and no control subject was detected with a mutant allele.

Conclusion: The results of present study illustrated that SNP rs1799063 was considered as a significant risk factor for developing CHD in females as compared to males. The study results showed that advancing age, gender, smoking, alcohol intake, blood pressure, height and weight were significant risk factors associated with coronary heart disease.

Key Words: Coronary Heart Disease, Prothrombin, Coagulation Factor II, CHD, Myocardial Infarction

INTRODUCTION

Coronary heart disease or CHD is a cardiovascular disorder which can mainly be characterized by development of atherosclerotic plaques in the coronary arteries. The development of plaque leads to narrowing of arteries leading to reduced myocardial perfusion and increase in the risk of myocardial infarction and sudden cardiac death. According to World Health Organization (2023), one-third of all global deaths are due to cardiovascular diseases, making it one of the leading concern of mortality worldwide. The pathophysiology of CHD is complex and includes both environmental and genetic factors. Factors such as lifestyle, smoking, hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus and obesity play an important role in development of the disease (1, 2). The family and twin studies show that genetics plays 40% to 60% role in the heritability of disease, thus making inherited genetic variation an important factor in the pathogenesis of CHD (3).

The gene *F2* or Coagulation Factor II is present on the short arm (p-arm) of chromosome 11 (11p^{11.2}). The gene is 21kb long and has 14 exons. It is responsible for coding a prothrombin protein, also called

coagulation factor II, which is cleaved proteolytically in multiple steps for the formation of an activated serine protease thrombin. This activated thrombin enzyme converts fibrinogen to fibrin during the formation of blood clot, by initiating aggregation of platelets in the process of thrombosis and hemostasis (4). The process of thrombosis play a strategic role in the pathophysiology of coronary heart diseases, followed by rupturing of atherosclerotic plaque. Prothrombin being the main component of the coagulation cascade, generates thrombin and fibrin clot formation. The variations in gene *F2* leads to an increase in coagulation, therefore increasing the risk of arterial and venous thrombotic events (5). The polymorphism in the G20210A in the 3' untranslated region of the gene *F2* has been reported to increase levels of the prothrombin in plasma, which leads to an increase in generation of thrombin and predisposing thrombosis carriers (6).

Many epidemiological studies have been done to evaluate the association of *F2* G20210A polymorphism and cardiovascular diseases such as myocardial infarction and CHD. However, findings of these studies are inconsistent across different populations.

National Press Associates. (2026). ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA).

Some studies have reported a significant association between F2 variant and risk of CHD, while others suggest there is a non-significant effect. The differences in the results could be due to ethnic differences, gene-environment interactions and study design differences (7). Moreover, the data is limited, which highlights the need for genetic investigations based on specific populations.

The aim of the present case control study was to investigate whether the prothrombin gene variant plays a significant role in increasing the risk of coronary heart disease in the population of Malwa region of Punjab (India).

Material and Methods

The present study was conducted in the different districts of Malwa region of Punjab, in which a total of 400 subjects (200 cases and 200 controls) between the ages of 40 to 70 years were included. The ethical clearance was taken from Institutional Ethics Committee. The study included both male and female participants. The clinically diagnosed, proved cases of coronary heart disease who provided written and informed consent were included as cases and subjects with no comorbidities or the related diseases who gave written and informed consent were included as controls.

A self-prepared questionnaire was used to collect anthropometric, physiological and demographic data. The data related to place of residence, smoking status, alcohol consumption, physical activity and time of onset was recorded. For genotype analysis, 2ml of venous blood was collected in EDTA vials by trained technician from both cases and controls and DNA was extracted using

standard salting out DNA extraction method given by Miller *et al.* (1988) (8). After extracting the DNA, the quality and quantity analysis was done, the ratio of 260/280nm was calculated and DNA samples for which ratio was between 1.7 – 1.9 were considered for further PCR RFLP analysis in the present study. The extracted DNA samples were stored at -20°C to preserve the integrity of the extracted DNA. The specific set of primers FP 5'-TCTAGAAACAGTTGCCTGGC-3' and RP 5'-ATAGCACTGGGAGCATTGAAGC-3' for SNP rs1799963 were designed using primer blast tool for amplifying 345bp long fragment of DNA. The obtained PCR product was digested using restriction enzyme *HindIII*. For the digestion of amplicon, 3ul of restriction enzyme was added to 10ul of PCR reaction mixture with 4ul of buffer and 8ul of nuclease-free water. The PCR tubes containing reaction mixture and the restriction enzyme were kept overnight at 37°C in water bath. Digested product was checked using 4% ethidium bromide-stained agarose gel and a DNA ladder of 100bp was used to measure the amplicon size. The gel was then visualized on Gel Doc system and photographs were taken.

Results

The genotyping of the SNP rs1799963 (G/A) was done using restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP). The specific set of primers were used for amplifying the 345bp long fragment. The PCR product was then digested using *HindIII* restriction enzyme by keeping it overnight in the water bath at 37°C and the products were checked using 4% ethidium bromide-stained agarose gel.

National Press Associates. (2026). ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA).

The homozygous products were digested into 322bp and 16bp fragments and the heterozygous yielded three bands of 345, 322 and 16bp fragments. The results of genotyping showed that the both case and control groups had greater percentage of wild allele type whereas only CHD patients had a mutant allele. The differences in allele frequencies were statistically significant for cases and controls ($p = 0.0001$, OR = 0.025; 95% CI = 0.001-0.43). For wild type G

allele, the cases had a frequency of 95.5% (382/400) and for controls, it was 100% (400/400) whereas, for mutant allele A, the cases showed a frequency of 4.5% (18/400) and no control subject was detected with mutant allele. The genotypic distribution showed that the homozygous wild type (G/G) was 92%, homozygous mutant type (A/A) was 1% and the heterozygous genotype (G/A) was 7%.

Table 1: Frequency distribution of studied genotype of rs1799963

Genotype	Cases n (%) N=200	Controls n (%) N=200	OR (95% CI)	p-value
G/G	184 (92%)	200 (100%)	Referent	
G/A	14 (7%)	0	0.03 (0.001-0.53)	0.0001*
A/A	2 (1%)	0	0.18 (0.008-3.86)	0.14

OR: Odds Ratio; CI: Confidence Interval; n= frequency of particular genotype in the cases and controls group; N= total number of cases and controls; * $p < 0.05$ was considered as statistical significant.

When the samples were stratified on the basis of gender, it was observed that females had higher risk of developing CHD because

frequency of heterozygous genotype was higher in females (12.8%) as compared to their male counterparts (1.9%). The frequency of mutant homozygous allele was 2.1% in females and in males, it was absent. Statistically significant differences were observed in heterozygous genotype (G/A) for female cases and their control peers ($p= 0.0002$, OR= 0.032; 95% CI= 0.001-0.54).

Table 2: Association of rs1799963 genotypes in CHD patients and controls (stratified by gender)

Genotype	Cases n (%) N=200	Controls n (%) N=200	OR (95% CI)	p-value
MALES				
G/G	104 (98.1%)	100	Referent	
G/A	2 (1.9%)	0	0.20 (0.009-4.38)	0.16
A/A	0	0		
FEMALES				
G/G	80 (85.1%)	100	Referent	

National Press Associates. (2026). ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA).

G/A	12 (12.8%)	0	0.032 (0.001-0.54)	0.0002*
A/A	2 (2.2%)	0	0.16 (0.007-3.38)	0.11

OR: Odds Ratio; CI: Confidence Interval; n= frequency of particular genotype in the cases and controls group; N= total number of cases and controls; *p < 0.05 was considered as statistical significant.

The association between all three different genotypes (G/G, G/A, A/A) and anthropometric, physiological and demographic parameters for SNP rs1799963 was done for CHD patients and controls. Statistically significant differences were observed in genotypes for gender (p = 0.003), systolic blood pressure (SBP) (p = 0.009), diastolic blood pressure (DBP) (p =

0.01) and working hours (p < 0.0001). It was observed that for wild type genotype, CHD in males (56.5%) was more prevalent as compared to CHD in females (43.5%) and majority of the subjects belonged to rural areas (56%). In males, only 17.4% were smokers and 23.4% consumed alcohol. Only 50% of the subjects were active physically and had their mean working hours between 7.4±1.5 hours per day. While greater number of females (85.7%) with CHD had GA genotype as compared to their male counterparts (14.3%). None of the cases with heterozygous genotypes were smokers and only 7% of them consumed alcohol.

Table 3: Comparison of different demographic, anthropometric and clinical variables among different genotypes of rs1799963 in CHD patients

Variable	Genotype (G/G)	Genotype (G/A)	Genotype (A/A)	p-value
GENDER				
Male	56.5%	0%	14.3%	0.003*
Female	43.5%	100%	85.7%	
RESIDENCE				
Urban	44%	0%	35.7%	0.38
Rural	56%	100%	64.3%	
SMOKING				
Never	82.6%	100%	100%	0.19
Ever	17.4%	0%	0%	
ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION				
Never	76.6%	100%	92.9%	0.27
Ever	23.4%	0%	7.1%	
PHYSICAL ACTIVITY				
Unemployed	50%	100%	64.3%	
Employed	50%	0%	35.7%	
BMI	25.9 ± 2.8	23.2 ± 1.9	24.2 ± 4.65	0.06
SBP (mmHg)	122.5 ± 20.8	135 ± 7	139 ± 18.9	0.009*

National Press Associates. (2026). ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA).

(Mean ± SD)				
DBP (mmHg) (Mean ± SD)	81.7 ± 11.6	85 ± 7	91.1 ± 13.3	0.01*
Working Hours (per day)	7.4 ± 1.5	-	8.2 ± 0.84	<0.0001*
TIME OF ONSET OF DISEASE				
≤ 1 year	53.8%	100%	21.4%	0.31
More than 1 year	46.2%	0%	78.6%	

BMI = Body Mass Index; SBP = Systolic Blood Pressure; SD = Standard Deviation; *p < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant

Table 4: Association of prothrombin rs1799963 SNP with coronary heart disease.

Model	Genotype	Cases (N=200)	Controls (N=200)	p-value
Dominant	G/G	184 (92%)	200 (100%)	<0.0001*
	G/A – A/A	16 (8%)	0 (0%)	
Recessive	G/G – G/A	198 (99%)	200 (100%)	0.15
	A/A	2 (1%)	0 (0%)	
Overdominant	G/G – A/A	186 (93%)	200 (100%)	0.0001*
	G/A	14 (7%)	0 (0%)	

N= number of individuals; *p < 0.05 statistically significant

DISCUSSION

In the present study, no females consumed alcohol, therefore alcohol consumption (41.5%) was taken as a risk factor for males only. The results of the present study were similar with the study done by De *et al.* (2013) in West Bengal where 22.52% of males consumed alcohol and a study done by Kar *et al.* (2010) in northern India where alcohol consumption was found to be in 54% of the male population (9, 10). Several studies done in different areas reported that alcohol consumption was present in 12.5 percent of subjects living in Rajasthan, 28% of males from Chennai, 10 percent of subjects from Punjab and 16.2 percent of males and 0.9 percent of females from

Vietnam consumed alcohol (11-14). In the year 2014, Shridhar *et al.* reported that 13.5% of the subjects consumed alcohol. These results were similar with the present study that, alcohol has an effect on the health of coronary heart disease patients, but it can't be considered as a risk factor in the female population, due to less number of females consuming alcohol. But a large number of males consumed alcohol in the present study and the other studies (15).

The coagulation factors are a group of proteins which are essential for natural clotting of blood. One of such coagulation factor is prothrombin, also known as coagulation factor II, which is a precursor of thrombin and plays an important role in the

National Press Associates. (2026). ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA).

formation of fibrin. The prothrombin mutation was first studied by Poort *et al.* in 1996. The mutation at 20210 at 3'-untranslated region of coagulation factor II gene from G to A was detected. In his study, the results showed only 1% of subjects had homozygous mutant genotype (AA) for polymorphism of prothrombin G20210A (rs1799963). Homozygous wild type genotype was present in 92% of the subjects, whereas only 7% of the subjects were heterozygous (GA). There were statistically non-significant differences between wild and mutant type genotype. It was also concluded, that only females had mutant type genotype and the results were statistically non-significant. Cases with heterozygous genotype had more percentage of patients (78.6%) who had disease onset time more than one year, as compared to cases with wild type genotype (53.8%), who had disease onset time less than or equal to one year. Many studies have reported association of prothrombin gene with different diseases in different populations. The mutation in SNP rs1799963 was found in 1% to 3% of controls and 6% to 8% in cases (16-20) whereas, in the present study, none of the controls had mutant or heterozygous genotype. The results of the present study were dissimilar to the study done by Eichinger *et al.* (1999), Kearon *et al.* (1999), Lensing and Prins (1999) and Lindmarker *et al.* (1999) who reported mutation in rs1799963 as a risk factor for recurrent venous thromboembolism (21-24).

In year 2019, Khantalin *et al.* concluded that a case presenting with recurrent coronary syndromes had an increase in levels of lipoprotein a and variation in the SNP

rs1799963 prothrombin genetic variant was found to be associated with an increased risk of thromboembolism (25). According to the meta-analysis, the association between the SNP rs1799963 and CHD have shown uncertain results. They also reported that there is non-significant overall association between G20210A variant and CHD risk in the general population. Whereas, other studies have reported that, in younger individuals and populations with individuals with less cardiovascular risk factors, have a significant association between the G20210A variant and myocardial infarction (6, 7, 26, 27). These studies illustrated that SNP rs1799963 may act as a risk factor than a primary cause for the early onset of CHD. For rs1799963, the GG variant was present predominately in both cases and controls, but it was more frequent in cases, whereas the heterozygous GA genotype was present in only 8.4% of controls and 2.0% of cases. There was no case or control with AA genotype. The distribution of genotype was reported to be in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium in their study. The results of their study did not confirm to the results of present study, because in the present frequency distribution of GG genotype was more in both cases and controls.

The variability of results in different studies can be due to different ethnicities of the observed population. There is a difference in frequency of 20210A allele in different ethnic groups, prevalence being higher in people of European ancestry and rare in Asian and African population. These differences affect the statistical differences and justify the differences in findings among

National Press Associates. (2026). ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA).

case-control studies conducted in different populations.

CONCLUSION

The results of present concluded that age was found to be a risk factor for developing coronary heart disease. The rs1799963 was considered as a significant risk factor for developing CHD in females as compared to males. The present study concluded that advancing age, gender, smoking, alcohol intake, blood pressure, height and weight were significant risk factors associated with coronary heart disease. Hence, there is a need for more such studies with large number of sample size for more substantial results. There is need of large scale studies with more variants of prothrombin gene are suggested, which would help in understanding the effect of polymorphisms on the development of coronary heart disease in the presence of additional risk factor.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank all the participants who gave their consent to participate in this study.

Funding

The authors are thankful for the funding received from one of the higher education agency.

Conflict of Interest

There is no potential conflict of interest relevant to this article was reported.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. (2023). Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs).

National Press Associates. (2026). ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA).

Research & Reviews in Biotechnology & Biosciences, 13(1), 70–80

2. Yusuf S, Hawken S, Ounpuu S, Dans T, Avezum A, Lanas F, McQueen M, Budaj A, Pais P, Varigos J, Lisheng L; INTERHEART Study Investigators. Effect of potentially modifiable risk factors associated with myocardial infarction in 52 countries (the INTERHEART study): case-control study. *Lancet*. 2004 Sep 11-17;364(9438):937-52.
3. McPherson R, Tybjaerg-Hansen A. Genetics of Coronary Artery Disease. *Circ Res*. 2016 Feb 19;118(4):564-78. <https://doi.org/10.1161/circresaha.115.306566>
4. F2 coagulation factor II, thrombin [Homo sapiens (human)] - Gene - NCBI. (n.d.). www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/2147>
5. Aikkal, Riju. (2025). The Role of F2 (Prothrombin) in Coagulation and Thrombosis. 10.13140/RG.2.2.19631.04002.
6. Li, C., Ren, H., Chen, H. et al. Prothrombin G20210A (rs1799963) polymorphism increases myocardial infarction risk in an age-related manner: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sci Rep* 2017;7:13550. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-13623-6>
7. Burzotta, F, Paciaroni K, De Stefano V, Crea F, Maseri A, Leone G et al. G20210A prothrombin gene polymorphism and coronary ischaemic syndromes: a phenotype-

- specific meta-analysis of 12 034 subjects. *Heart (British Cardiac Society)* 2004;90:82–86.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/heart.90.1.82>
8. Miller SA, Dykes DD, Polesky HF. A simple salting out procedure for extracting DNA from human nucleated cells. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 1988 Feb 11;16(3):1215.
 9. Comparative Study of Risk Factors of Cardiac Diseases among Urban and Rural Population. *International Journal of Human Genetics* 2013;13.
<https://doi.org/10.31901/24566330.2013/13.01.03>
 10. Kar SS, Thakur JS, Viridi NK, Jain S, Kumar R. Risk factors for cardiovascular diseases: is the social gradient reversing in northern India? *Natl Med J India.* 2010 Jul-Aug;23(4):206-9.
 11. Pandey, S., Pandey, S., Purushottam Anshul Jhanwar, & Jhanwar. A prospective study of Myocardial Infarction patients admitted in a tertiary care hospital of south-eastern Rajasthan a b * c d 2012:3.
 12. Gajalakshmi V, Lacey B, Kanimozhi V, Sherliker P, Peto R, Lewington S. Body-mass index, blood pressure, and cause-specific mortality in India: a prospective cohort study of 500 810 adults. *Lancet Glob Health.* 2018 Jul;6(7):e787-e794.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s2214-109x\(18\)30267-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2214-109x(18)30267-5)
 13. Gorea R, & Bal MS. Atherosclerosis in Coronaries in Malwa Region of Punjab. *ResearchGate* 2005;27(4):236.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/236624239_Atherosclerosis_in_Coronaries_in_Malwa_Region_of_Punjab
 14. Hien HA, Tam NM, Tam V, Derese A, Devroey D. Prevalence, Awareness, Treatment, and Control of Hypertension and Its Risk Factors in (Central) Vietnam. *Int J Hypertens.* 2018 May 16;2018:6326984.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/6326984>
 15. Shridhar K, Dhillon PK, Bowen L, Kinra S, Bharathi AV, Prabhakaran D, Reddy KS, Ebrahim S; Indian Migration Study Group. The association between a vegetarian diet and cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk factors in India: the Indian Migration Study. *PLoS One.* 2014 Oct 24;9(10):e110586.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0110586>
 16. Poort SR, Rosendaal FR, Reitsma PH, Bertina RM. A common genetic variation in the 3'-untranslated region of the prothrombin gene is associated with elevated plasma prothrombin levels and an increase in venous thrombosis. *Blood.* 1996 Nov 15;88(10):3698-703.
 17. Ferraresi P, Marchetti G, Legnani C, Cavallari E, Castoldi E, Mascoli F, Ardissino D, Palareti G, Bernardi F. The heterozygous 20210 G/A prothrombin genotype is associated with early venous thrombosis in

National Press Associates. (2026). ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA).

- inherited thrombophilias and is not increased in frequency in artery disease. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol.* 1997 Nov;17(11):2418-22. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.atv.17.11.2418>
18. Hillarp A, Zöller B, Svensson PJ, Dahlbäck B. The 20210 A allele of the prothrombin gene is a common risk factor among Swedish outpatients with verified deep venous thrombosis. *Thromb Haemost.* 1997 Sep;78(3):990-2.
 19. Leroyer C, Mercier B, Oger E, Chenu E, Abgrall JF, Férec C, Mottier D. Prevalence of 20210 A allele of the prothrombin gene in venous thromboembolism patients. *Thromb Haemost.* 1998 Jul;80(1):49-51. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0037-1615137>
 20. Rosendaal FR, Doggen CJ, Zivelin A, Arruda VR, Aiach M, Siscovick DS, Hillarp A, Watzke HH, Bernardi F, Cumming AM, Preston FE, Reitsma PH. Geographic distribution of the 20210 G to A prothrombin variant. *Thromb Haemost.* 1998 Apr;79(4):706-8.
 21. Eichinger A, Beisel HG, Jacob U, Huber R, Medrano FJ, Banbula A, Potempa J, Travis J, Bode W. Crystal structure of gingipain R: an Arg-specific bacterial cysteine proteinase with a caspase-like fold. *EMBO J.* 1999 Oct 15;18(20):5453-62. <https://doi.org/10.1093/emboj/18.20.5453>
 22. Kearon C, Gent M, Hirsh J, Weitz J, Kovacs MJ, Anderson DR, Turpie AG, Green D, Ginsberg JS, Wells P, MacKinnon B, Julian JA. A comparison of three months of anticoagulation with extended anticoagulation for a first episode of idiopathic venous thromboembolism. *N Engl J Med.* 1999 Mar 25;340(12):901-7. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejm199903253401201>
 23. Lensing AW, Prins MH. Recurrent deep vein thrombosis and two coagulation factor gene mutations: quo vadis? *Thromb Haemost.* 1999 Dec;82(6):1564-6.
 24. Lindmarker P, Schulman S, Sten-Linder M, Wiman B, Egberg N, Johnsson H. The risk of recurrent venous thromboembolism in carriers and non-carriers of the G1691A allele in the coagulation factor V gene and the G20210A allele in the prothrombin gene. DURAC Trial Study Group. Duration of Anticoagulation. *Thromb Haemost.* 1999 May;81(5):684-9. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0037-1614554>
 25. Khantalin I, Blanchard V, Viallet N, Lambert G. Recurrent coronary syndromes in a patient with isolated very-high lipoprotein (a) and the prothrombin genetic variant rs1799963 (G20210A): a case report. *Eur Heart J Case Rep.* 2019 Feb 25;3(1):ytz019. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ehjcr/ytz019>

National Press Associates. (2026). ASSOCIATION OF F2 GENE (RS1799963) POLYMORPHISM WITH THE CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN THE POPULATION OF MALWA REGION OF PUNJAB (INDIA).

26. Ye Z, Liu EH, Higgins JP, Keavney BD, Lowe GD, Collins R, Danesh J. Seven haemostatic gene polymorphisms in coronary disease: meta-analysis of 66,155 cases and 91,307 controls. *Lancet*. 2006 Feb 25;367(9511):651-8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes16121490>
27. Rosendaal FR, Siscovick DS, Schwartz SM, Beverly RK, Psaty BM, Longstreth WT Jr, Raghunathan TE, Koepsell TD, Reitsma PH. Factor V Leiden (resistance to activated protein C) increases the risk of myocardial infarction in young women. *Blood*. 1997 Apr 15;89(8):2817-21.